

MENTAL ILLNESS

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ABSTRACT

Mental illness has increasingly become a focus of discussion within many spheres of life such as classrooms, workplaces, and the media. This is not surprising considering that worldwide lifetime prevalence rates for developing a mental illness range between 18.1-36.1% . However, although attention to mental health issues is increasing , mental illnesses are still often referred to negatively and lead to discrimination . This may be due to the negative stereotypes associated with mental illnesses that shape what is referred to as stigma

Keywords: mental illness, growth, cognitive process.

INTRODUCTION

While research on the topics of mental illnesses and its stigma is growing, research targeting the experiences of specific groups, such as criminal offenders, is modest at best. However, the need for such research is mounting due to the rising number of individuals with mental illnesses within the criminal justice system . To address this gap, the primary objective of this study was to investigate the stigmatization of criminal offenders with mental illnesses within the context of a mock-juror scenario. In addition, this study explored the influence of the media on the formation of this stigma. Research has shown that the media greatly influences attitudes towards topics such as body image , substance use, and mental health. Therefore, the potential influence of the media on attitudes of potential jurors was included in this study as well.

Recently, research has begun to address this gap. Mossiere and Maeder conducted two studies examining the influence of a defendants' mental illness on jury verdicts. Mossiere and Maeder examined how juror verdicts varied depending on the mental illness of a defendant. Participants were asked to indicate their attitude towards mental illnesses, read a trial transcript and then provide a verdict for a defendant with one of four mental illnesses or no mental illness at all. The results of this research did not indicate that participants' attitudes or the mental illness of the defendant influenced verdict decisions. In the subsequent similar study, Mossier and Maeder again examined four mental illnesses but incorporated the use of a not criminally responsible on account of a mental disorder defense (NCRMD). This defense is used in instances in which an individual cannot understand the circumstances or gravity of the act they have

committed and/or did not know it was wrong due to a mental illness . Using similar methods, Mossier and Maeder found that participants were more likely to provide a guilty verdict to a defendant with substance abuse disorder and a verdict of NCRMD to the other three mental illnesses (schizophrenia, bipolar and depression). Due to the overrepresentation of individuals with mental illnesses in the criminal justice system and the potential for stigmatization of these individuals, more research of this nature is essential for fully understanding the role of mental illness stigma within the judicial process. The current study attempted to address this need by expanding on and replicating aspects of both studies previously conducted by Mossiere and Maeder.

The media has a strong role in reflecting and shaping perspectives towards varying issues. Mirroring the stereotypes previously mentioned, those with a mental illness are frequently represented in the media as violent and something to be feared . For example, research suggests that stories in the news regarding mental illnesses tend to focus on an association with dangerousness and criminality . Research has also found that witnessing negative depictions of mental illness within the media over time can have consequences such as being more likely to believe that these depictions are accurate and endorse these stereotypes as suitable and desiring greater social distance from those with mental illnesses . Previous research has also found that even brief media exposure can influence individual participants attitudes and beliefs towards many other topics. For example, Burriss, Brownlow and Linds found that participants perspectives on body image and fitness-related behaviors changed after reading about varying opinions regarding fitness in articles. Another study found that brief exposure to violence through video games increased hostile biases . Participants in this study played a violent or non-violent video game for 20 minutes and were then asked to read a story and state what the character in the story would do next. They found that exposure to violent video games resulted in participants expecting that situations with conflict would be dealt with aggressively by the character. Therefore, both short and long-term exposure to issues in the media can have a role in shaping attitudes towards varying issues.

The current study was completed online using the Qualtrics platform. To reduce socially desirable responding, participants were told that they would be participating in two independent studies, the first examining the effects of media on memory and the second examining juror decision-making. Participants began by first providing consent and then completing the media questionnaire. They were then randomly assigned to one of the three media conditions (i.e., positive, negative or neutral depictions of mental illnesses) in which they watched the video clips. The first manipulation check was introduced at this point. After viewing these videos, participants answered the memory test questions and were then randomly assigned to one of the three trial

transcript conditions (a defendant with schizophrenia, depression or no mental illness). After reading the trial transcript they completed the juror response form and responded to the stigma scales. Finally, participants answered demographic, mental health experiences, and funnel debriefing questions. The second manipulation check was presented after the demographic questions. Following these questions participants were debriefed.

CONCLUSION

Finally, it was predicted that the participants in both the negative media and schizophrenia mental illness conditions would provide the greatest number of guilty verdicts with the most confidence and have the most negative attitudes. The results returned no significant interaction between media and mental illnesses on either one of the stigma scales. However, a significant interaction was found between media and mental illnesses on verdict decisions. Additional Bonferroni post-hoc analysis revealed that when participants watched the control video depiction, there were significantly more not guilty verdicts provided with greater confidence when the defendant had schizophrenia compared to depression. In this case, the control video presumably had little effect on verdict decisions, meaning the defendants' mental illness primarily influenced these results.

As alluded to previously, one possible explanation for this effect relates to beliefs in criminal culpability for a crime committed. Within the legal domain the concept of criminal culpability suggests that responsibility for a crime requires that an individual possesses a degree of rationality when committing criminal behaviors that allows him or her to act in accordance with his or her personal free will and understand the consequences of his or her actions. The application of this principle to mental illness is known as the NCRMD defense, which was mentioned previously. Research has explored the relationship between free will and mental illnesses by examining public perceptions about the causes of and control one has over various mental illnesses.

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